

Towards Responsible and Sustainable Research Assessment
*Evidence, tools and lessons from the ReAss CoARA pilot at
FPCEE–Blanquerna, Ramon Llull University*

CoARA pilot project
Faculty of Psychology, Education and Sport Sciences (FPCEE),
Blanquerna – Universitat Ramon Llull

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Executive Summary

Research assessment systems across Europe are undergoing a profound transformation. Traditional models centred on quantitative, publication-based metrics have increasingly been shown to inadequately capture the diversity of research contributions, career trajectories, and forms of impact required in contemporary research ecosystems. In response, the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) and the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) promote a shift towards qualitative, transparent, and context-sensitive evaluation practices that better support fair assessment and sustainable research careers within the European Research Area.

The project *Towards a Qualitative Paradigm: Rethinking Research and Researchers Assessment at Blanquerna, Universitat Ramon Llull (ReAss)* was developed as an institutional pilot at the Faculty of Psychology, Education and Sport Sciences (FPCEE) of Blanquerna – Universitat Ramon Llull, with the objective of translating CoARA principles into concrete assessment practices. Building on a long-standing tradition of research evaluation, the project addressed clear limitations identified in existing models, notably their strong reliance on bibliometric indicators, limited recognition of diverse contributions, and insufficient sensitivity to career stages and collaborative research practices.

ReAss adopted an evidence-based and co-creation, participatory methodological approach, combining a longitudinal review of research assessment practices (2004–2024), a survey of researchers across all European research career stages (R1–R4), and a series of focus groups. These methods enabled a systematic analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in the existing system, while capturing researchers' perceptions, overlooked dimensions of research activity, and risks associated with metric-driven assessment cultures. Focus groups played a central role as deliberative spaces for collective reflection and cultural shift.

Through this iterative and reflexive process—reinforced by interinstitutional exchanges with other organisations committed to CoARA—the project identified *seven key dimensions of change* guiding the pilot: *broadening the conceptualisation of research quality*; embedding qualitative, narrative and peer-based assessment; ensuring inclusivity and researcher development across career stages; enhancing reflexivity, transparency and formative feedback; fostering researcher engagement and co-creation; reframing the role of assessment in career progression; and aligning individual and group-based assessment to support sustainable research environments. The emergence of the latter dimension highlighted the need to reconcile individual evaluation with team development and long-term research capacity building.

These dimensions were operationalised through a set of concrete outputs and innovations. Central among them is the Narrative CV Template – FPCEE Blanquerna, a qualitative and modular tool designed to recognise diverse research contributions across four domains: knowledge generation; researcher training and teamwork; contributions to the scientific and innovation community; and contributions to society, complemented by a reflective assessment of research trajectory and future strategy. The template was developed through iterative piloting and feedback involving 37 researchers from different career stages.

To support consistent and transparent evaluation, ReAss also developed a qualitative assessment rubric aligned with the European Framework for Research Careers, together with a GenAI-based decision-support model. This model provides structured qualitative analysis, formative feedback, and visualisations, complementing—rather than replacing—human assessment. Validation through

parallel human–AI assessments showed high levels of agreement, supporting its use as a scalable and responsible evaluation aid.

Recognising that assessment reform requires cultural change, the project placed strong emphasis on training and capacity-building actions, including multiple meetings, training sessions, and the development of training capsules addressing CoARA principles, narrative assessment, responsible metrics, among others.

Overall, the ReAss project demonstrates how research assessment reform can be implemented in practice through evidence, participation, and reflexivity. By aligning with both the core and supporting commitments of CoARA, it offers transferable tools, insights, and lessons for institutions seeking to advance fair, qualitative, and sustainable research assessment practices across Europe.

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1. Context and Rationale: Why Reforming Research Assessment Matters

1.1 European Policy Context

Across Europe, research systems are undergoing a profound transformation in how research quality, impact, and careers are assessed. For decades, evaluation practices have relied predominantly on quantitative, publication-based metrics, which have proven insufficient to capture the diversity of research contributions, trajectories, and societal roles expected from contemporary researchers. In response, European research policy has increasingly emphasised the need for more responsible, transparent, and context-sensitive assessment models that support research excellence while fostering integrity, openness, collaboration, and inclusive career development.

The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) and the establishment of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) mark a decisive shift towards qualitative, peer-review-centred evaluation approaches, the recognition of a broad range of scholarly contributions, and the abandonment of inappropriate uses of journal- and publication-level indicators. Within this evolving policy landscape, reforming research assessment is inseparable from rethinking research careers, as fair and holistic evaluation frameworks are essential to support diverse career paths, reduce structural biases, and align institutional practices with the values underpinning the European Research Area.

1.2. Institutional Context and Characteristics of the previous Assessment System

The Faculty of Psychology, Education and Sport Sciences (FPCEE) has a long-standing tradition of evaluating the research activity of its academic staff, dating back to the publication of its first formal evaluation criteria and procedures in October 2004. Research assessment, together with teaching evaluation, has traditionally been organised in three-year cycles, reflecting an institutional commitment to periodic monitoring of academic performance.

In preparation for the 2024–2029 General Research Plan (Pla General de Recerca, PGR), a collective reflection process was initiated to reconsider how academic research activity should be evaluated. This process began in February 2021 with discussions among the Vice-Deans of Research of the three faculties and subsequently evolved through consultations with the Directors of the Research Institutes. A preliminary draft of the revised assessment framework was iteratively refined and ultimately submitted for approval to the Blanquerna Research and Ethics Council (Comissió d'Ètica i Recerca, CER), ensuring institutional alignment and governance oversight.

The assessment targeted faculty members with officially recognised research time and pursued a dual purpose: to stimulate research activity and support individual career development strategies, while at the same time maintaining the quality standards required by external evaluation and accreditation agencies. Two specific objectives were identified. First, the need to generate evidence that would make visible research achievements not consistently captured through existing reporting channels, such as the institutional MERIT platform or research funding tracking systems. Second, the introduction of a validation mechanism to enable the pedagogical correction of misreported or incomplete records.

Beyond its evaluative function, the assessment tool was also conceived as a self-assessment instrument, allowing academic staff to benchmark their research performance against the expectations associated with their professional category. While formal evaluations continued to follow the

established three-year cycle, this reflective dimension aimed to foster greater awareness of research trajectories and development opportunities.

The assessment framework was structured around three main categories. Productivity (60% weight) focused primarily on research outputs, including impact-factor publications (JCR, SJR), books and book chapters (SPI), other scholarly publications, dissemination activities such as conference presentations, peer review contributions and editorial board memberships, as well as doctoral supervision and patents. Projects (35%) covered leadership or participation in both competitive and non-competitive research projects, with explicit recognition also given to unsuccessful competitive proposals as indicators of research engagement. Finally, Other merits (5%) encompassed research group leadership and research stays of at least one month.

In the latest call, 80 researchers participated, with 20% exempt due to external evaluation credentials. Of the remaining 64, 43% received a “very favourable” evaluation, 42% “favourable,” and 14% “unfavourable.” Each researcher received personalised feedback via email, including: an overall rating (very favourable, favourable, or not favourable), a score out of 100, the average and score range for their academic category, and the scoring table for each evaluation parameter.

Despite its robustness and internal coherence, this assessment system increasingly revealed structural limitations. Its firm reliance on output-based indicators, the uneven visibility of diverse research contributions, and the limited capacity to capture qualitative aspects of research practices and career trajectories highlighted the need for further development. In this context, the ReAss project emerged as a structured, evidence-based pilot designed to critically examine existing practices, systematically gather researchers’ perceptions, and develop alternative assessment tools aligned with European principles for responsible research assessment. The pilot sought not only to refine institutional evaluation mechanisms but also to generate transferable insights to support broader reform efforts within the European Research Area.

2. Project Overview: Objectives, Scope and Governance

2.1 Objectives

The main aim of the project is to pilot a reform of research and researcher assessment practices at the School of Psychology, Education, and Sport Science of the University Ramon Llull. To do so, we aim to:

- a) Recognise diverse types of research contributions
- b) Promote a broad consideration of research quality and societal impact,
- c) Foster inclusivity, peer review, openness and collaboration among researchers.

Additionally, we aim to understand the challenges, biases, and researchers’ attitudes when adopting new research assessment criteria, as well as to reflect on the culture of research assessment that has developed over time.

2.2 Scope and Target Groups

The ReAss project was designed as an institutional pilot addressing research assessment as a shared practice that affects multiple actors within the research ecosystem. Its scope, therefore, extended beyond individual researchers to include the broader institutional structures and roles involved in evaluation and career development.

The primary target group consisted of researchers across all stages of the academic career, in accordance with the European Framework for Research Careers (R1–R4). These researchers were the main beneficiaries of the pilot, as the project aimed to develop assessment tools and criteria capable of recognising diverse research contributions, trajectories, and forms of impact, while supporting fair and sustainable career development.

In addition, the project targeted evaluators, members of assessment panels, academic leaders, and other institutional actors responsible for research governance and quality assurance. This group was essential to ensure that the proposed reforms were not only conceptually aligned with European principles but also operationally feasible, institutionally embedded, and capable of informing decision-making processes beyond the pilot phase.

2.3 Governance and Promoting Team

The ReAss project adopted a structured, nested governance model to ensure strategic oversight, operational efficiency, and broad institutional engagement. A defining feature of this model was the systematic inclusion of researchers representing all stages of the European Framework for Research Careers, ranging from early-stage researchers (R1), recognised researchers (R2), and established researchers (R3), to leading researchers (R4).

At the strategic level, a Steering Committee (SC) was established, bringing together institutional leadership in research and quality assurance, directors of the research institutes, and representatives of researchers from different career stages.

The Steering Committee was responsible for defining strategic priorities, allocating budgetary and staff resources, and endorsing the overall work plan. In addition, it oversaw the design of focus groups and workshops to communicate the pilot objectives and mobilise researcher participation.

Nested within the Steering Committee, an Executive Committee (EC) was appointed to operationalise and implement the activities defined in the work plan. The EC brought together institutional research leadership and representatives from each research career stage, ensuring continuity between strategic decision-making and day-to-day execution. This configuration facilitated agile coordination, close monitoring of progress, and iterative adjustments based on emerging evidence and community feedback.

Finally, an Advisory Board (AB) was established as an overarching layer to monitor, support, and, when necessary, endorse key decisions taken by the Steering Committee. The Advisory Board included senior institutional governance representatives, as well as key actors responsible for research infrastructure and data management at both faculty and university levels. By embedding the project within existing governance structures while maintaining a clear distribution of roles, this nested committee system strengthened institutional ownership, enhanced accountability, and supported the sustainable integration of research assessment reform beyond the pilot.

3. Methodological Approach: Evidence-Based and Co-Creation Design

3.1. Review of Current and Previous Practices

As a first step, the project conducted a systematic review of research assessment practices at FPCEE–Blanquerna over a twenty-year period (2004–2024). This review analysed the evolution of

evaluation criteria, procedures, tools, and governance arrangements across multiple assessment cycles, drawing on institutional documentation and archival records. The analysis enabled a comprehensive assessment of the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of the existing model and supported the identification of the main structural challenges to be addressed by the ReAss pilot.

The analysis highlighted several strengths, including the long-standing institutionalisation and continuity of research evaluation, the use of structured and transparent procedures, and the integration of research assessment within broader quality assurance mechanisms. The formative intent of the evaluation process and the provision of individualised feedback were also identified as positive features supporting researcher awareness and accountability.

At the same time, the review revealed significant weaknesses. These included a strong dependence on quantitative and bibliometric indicators, limited recognition of diverse research contributions such as knowledge transfer, societal impact, and interdisciplinary work, and a rigid scoring model with limited sensitivity to disciplinary diversity and career stage differences. In addition, peer review and reflexive dialogue on research quality were only marginally embedded in existing practices.

The review also identified key opportunities for reform. These encompassed the potential to broaden the conceptualisation of research quality, introduce qualitative and narrative-based assessment tools, strengthen researcher development and inclusivity across career stages, and align institutional practices more closely with emerging European principles for responsible research assessment. In particular, the institution's mission-oriented research profile and strong engagement with societal stakeholders were seen as assets that could be better reflected in evaluation criteria.

Finally, several threats were identified that could hinder reform if not carefully addressed. These included cultural resistance to moving beyond established metric-based practices, concerns regarding the perceived objectivity and legitimacy of qualitative assessment, and external pressures from national and international evaluation systems that continue to prioritise quantitative indicators. Together, these findings underscored the need for a carefully designed, evidence-based pilot capable of building trust while navigating structural and cultural constraints.

For a detailed account, see:

[Morejon, S., Andrés, A., & Castelló, M. \(2025\). Report of Research Assessment Practices at Blanquerna, URL in the last 20 years: 2004-2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18035373>](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18035373)

3.2. Researcher-Centred Data Collection: Survey and Focus Groups

To complement the institutional review, the project implemented a survey for researchers at FPCEE–Blanquerna, combining quantitative and qualitative questions and explicitly accounting for differences across research career stages (R1–R4). The survey provided insight into researchers' perceptions of the current evaluation system, including perceived strengths, weaknesses, overlooked dimensions, opportunities for improvement, and risks associated with metric-driven assessment cultures.

While respondents generally valued the standardisation of criteria, institutional follow-up, and the formative intent of the evaluation process, they consistently highlighted limitations related to the narrow range of recognised contributions, the dominance of bibliometric indicators, and the tensions generated by workload distribution and role overlap. The survey also surfaced concerns regarding potential negative effects of metric-oriented evaluation, such as demotivation, ethical pressures,

misalignment with accreditation systems, and the risk of disengagement from socially relevant or interdisciplinary research.

In addition, focus groups were organised with 40 researchers from different disciplines and career stages. These sessions functioned as deliberative spaces to explore shared concerns in greater depth and collectively reflect on how assessment practices shape research behaviours, career development, and institutional culture.

For a detailed account, see:

[Garcia-Morante, M., Díaz, L., & Castelló, M \(2025\). Researcher-Centered Data Collection: Survey and Focus Groups results. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18035666>](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18035666)

3.3. Co-Creation, Iteration and Definition of Dimensions of Change

Building on the combined evidence from the review of practices, the survey, the focus groups, and interinstitutional exchanges with other organisations committed to CoARA, the ReAss project adopted a co-creative and iterative approach to defining its core dimensions of change. These dimensions emerged through a process of collective reflection, empirical grounding, and external reflexivity, and they structure both the analytical framework of the pilot and the design of its concrete tools and actions.

Participation in three interinstitutional learning events, including a dedicated session at the Institute of Bioengineering of Catalonia (IBEC) on 17 July 2025, reinforced the reflexive character of the project by situating institutional challenges within a broader European reform landscape. These exchanges enabled critical comparison, peer feedback, and validation of emerging approaches beyond the local context, strengthening the robustness and transferability of the proposed model.

As a result of this process, seven interrelated dimensions of change were identified and collectively endorsed:

1. **Broadening the Conceptualisation of Research Quality**
Moving beyond narrow, output-based definitions of excellence to recognise diverse forms of knowledge production, impact, and engagement, including open science, interdisciplinary work, and societal contribution.
2. **Embedding Qualitative, Narrative and Peer-Based Assessment**
Shifting the centre of assessment towards qualitative judgement supported by narrative accounts and peer review, with quantitative indicators used responsibly and contextually.
3. **Ensuring Researcher Development and Inclusivity Across Career Stages**
Designing assessment practices that are sensitive to different career phases (R1–R4), trajectories, and roles, and that support development rather than penalise non-linear careers.
4. **Enhancing Reflexivity, Transparency and Formative Feedback**
Strengthening dialogic assessment processes, clarity of criteria, and the formative function of evaluation in order to build trust, legitimacy, and learning-oriented assessment cultures.
5. **Fostering Researcher Engagement and Co-Creation**
Actively involving researchers in the design, discussion, and refinement of assessment

criteria and tools, recognising engagement as a prerequisite for sustainable reform.

6. Reframing the Role of Assessment in Career Progression

Opening a structured, long-term discussion on how assessment outcomes relate to recognition, research time allocation, promotion, and career advancement, in alignment with CoARA principles.

7. Aligning Individual and Group-Based Assessment to Support Sustainable Research Environments

Addressing the tension between individual performance evaluation and collective research practices by recognising collaborative roles, team science, and shared responsibility for research quality, with the aim of fostering resilient and sustainable research ecosystems.

These seven dimensions provided a shared analytical and normative framework guiding the pilot implementation and informed the development of all subsequent tools, including the Narrative CV, qualitative rubrics, and training materials.

For a detailed account, see:

[Garcia-Morante, M. & Castelló, M \(2025\). Presentation at the Scientific Seminar “Reforming Research Assessment”. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18035873>](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18035873)

4. Key Outputs and Innovations: From Analysis to Concrete Tools

4.1 Narrative CV Template

One of the principal outputs of the ReAss project is the development of the Narrative CV Template – FPCEE Blanquerna, a qualitative assessment tool designed to operationalise the principles of research assessment reform within the institutional context. The template is the result of a collaborative and iterative development process and constitutes a concrete innovation aligned with the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) and the objectives of CoARA.

The design of the Narrative CV was grounded in an extensive review of national and international narrative CV models promoted by major research funding and evaluation bodies, including research councils and universities that have pioneered qualitative and portfolio-based assessment approaches. These good practices were critically analysed and adapted to the specific institutional, disciplinary, and regulatory context of FPCEE–Blanquerna, ensuring compatibility with national and regional quality assurance requirements while maintaining alignment with European reform principles.

The development process followed a phased and participatory methodology. An initial version of the template was piloted internally by a small group of researchers and members of the project’s Executive Committee, resulting in several cycles of refinement of its structure, content, and guidance. Subsequently, the template was discussed with researchers external to the project team, whose expert and critical feedback contributed to improving its clarity, relevance, and usability. A final piloting phase involved 37 researchers¹ from different career stages, allowing the integration of diverse perspectives and ensuring sensitivity to heterogeneous trajectories and roles.

¹ A total of 45 researchers were invited to participate in the piloting phase; 37 of them completed and submitted the Narrative CV used for the pilot evaluation.

Structurally, the Narrative CV combines contextual and reflective elements with a modular organisation of research contributions over the previous three years. It includes: (1) essential personal information and career stage; (2) a concise narrative overview of the research trajectory; (3) four contribution modules addressing knowledge generation, researcher training and teamwork, contributions to the scientific and innovation community, and contributions to society; and (4) a reflective assessment focused on motivations, values, future objectives, and alignment with team development. An annex allows the structured listing of key outputs, supported by contextual indicators and the CRediT taxonomy to clarify individual roles.

A distinctive feature of the template is its explicit attempt to bridge individual and group-based perspectives in research assessment, recognising roles and shared responsibility, as well as the alignment between the individual projection and the group strategy. In this way, the Narrative CV supports a more holistic and sustainable approach to evaluation, capable of valuing diverse contributions while fostering research environments oriented towards long-term capacity building rather than short-term productivity.

For a detailed account, see:

[Castelló, M., et al. \(2025\). Narrative CV Template – FPCEE Blanquerna.](#)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18036156>

4.2. Assessment Tools and GenAI Integration

To complement the Narrative CV Template and ensure its consistent, transparent, and scalable use in research assessment processes, the ReAss project developed a set of assessment tools combining a qualitative evaluation rubric with a Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI)-based support model.

At the core of the assessment framework lies a qualitative rubric specifically designed to evaluate Narrative CVs in alignment with the European Framework for Research Careers (R1–R4). The rubric translates the four contribution modules of the Narrative CV into structured evaluation criteria, enabling assessors to consider the relevance, coherence, and quality of contributions in relation to the researcher's career stage and context.

Rather than assigning value based on predefined quantitative thresholds, the rubric supports reasoned qualitative judgement, encouraging evaluators to justify assessments through evidence provided in the narrative and its annexes. This approach enhances transparency and comparability while avoiding the inappropriate use of bibliometric indicators. By embedding career-stage sensitivity and recognising diverse roles and contributions, the rubric reinforces the formative and developmental function of research assessment.

Building on this rubric, the project developed a GenAI-based system to support the qualitative evaluation of Narrative CVs. The tool was conceived explicitly as a decision-support mechanism, designed to complement—not replace—human evaluation by providing structured analysis, feedback, and visualisation.

The system takes Narrative CVs as input and automatically segments them according to the predefined CV modules. Each module is then analysed using the qualitative rubric, tuned to the researcher's career stage (R1–R4). The evaluation process is implemented through a multi-agent architecture, in which dedicated agents assess each module, extract supporting evidence from the

narrative and linked materials, and generate structured outputs that include rubric-based assessments and documented justifications.

In parallel, a second analytical layer produces a SWOT analysis and a concise interpretative commentary for each module, offering formative feedback to researchers. These outputs are subsequently synthesised into a structured report, including visual representations (e.g. radar plots) that provide an intuitive overview of strengths, areas for development, and coherence across contribution domains.

For a detailed account, see:

[Castelló, M., et al. \(2025\). GenAI Assessment Rubric – FPCEE Blanquerna.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18036156>](#)

4.2.1. Development, Validation and Responsible Use

The GenAI model has been developed through an iterative, expert-informed process that closely aligns with the design of the Narrative CV and the qualitative rubric. Successive testing and calibration cycles compared AI-generated assessments with human evaluations, enabling adjustments to prompts, rubric interpretation, and output consistency. Validation through parallel human–AI assessments yielded high agreement (exceeding 80%), demonstrating the model’s capacity to support reliable, consistent qualitative evaluation.

Validation is understood as an ongoing process. Continuous monitoring and refinement are foreseen to mitigate potential biases, adapt to evolving assessment frameworks, and ensure responsible use in line with CoARA principles.

For a detailed account, see:

[Mulero, A., Garcia-Morante, M., Castelló, M. \(2025\). Towards a Gen-AI Assisted Model for CoARA-Aligned Researcher Assessment.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18036535>](#)

4.3. Training and Capacity-Building Actions

Recognising that research assessment reform requires not only new tools but also a profound cultural shift, the ReAss project placed strong emphasis on training, awareness-raising, and capacity-building actions throughout its implementation. These activities were conceived as essential enablers to support understanding, uptake, and responsible use of the Narrative CV, the qualitative rubric, and the GenAI-supported assessment model.

Throughout the project, 14 meetings and training sessions were organised with different stakeholder groups, including researchers at various career stages, research leaders, and institutional decision-makers. These sessions served multiple purposes: to introduce the principles of research assessment reform and the CoARA framework; to explain the rationale behind the new tools; to clarify expectations and address concerns; and to create spaces for dialogue and feedback. By fostering direct interaction, these meetings helped build trust, reduce uncertainty, and strengthen institutional ownership of the reform process.

In parallel, the project developed a set of training capsules as a core capacity-building resource. These short, modular training materials were designed to present key concepts related to research assessment

reform in a clear, accessible, and reusable format. The capsules address topics such as the principles of CoARA, the logic and structure of the Narrative CV, responsible metrics, and alternative indicators.

Together, these meetings and materials have enabled a progressive familiarisation of the research community with new assessment practices. By linking training directly to the concrete tools developed within ReAss, these actions strengthened the conditions for sustainable adoption and helped consolidate a shared understanding of responsible, qualitative, and career-sensitive research assessment practices.

For a detailed account, see:

<https://www.researcher-identity.com/reass>

[Castelló, M., Andrés, A. & Morejon, S. \(2025\) Internal presentations of the Re-Ass proposal.](#)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18036783>

5. Alignment with CoARA Commitments

Table 1

Alignment of the ReAss Project With CoARA Commitments

CoARA commitment	How the ReAss project supports the commitment	Key outputs / evidence
Core commitment 1: Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research	The project adopts a narrative and contextualised assessment approach that recognises diverse research outputs, roles, impacts, and career trajectories across all research career stages (R1–R4), including collaborative, interdisciplinary, and societal contributions.	Narrative CV Template; modular contribution structure; career-stage sensitivity
Core commitment 2: Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators	Research assessment is centred on qualitative, rubric-based judgement informed by narrative evidence and peer review. Quantitative indicators are used only for contextualisation and never as proxies for quality.	Qualitative rubric; Narrative CV Template; GenAI decision-support model
Core commitment 3: Abandon inappropriate uses of journal- and publication-based metrics (e.g., JIF, h-index)	Fixed metric thresholds and journal-based indicators are explicitly removed from evaluation criteria. Researchers are invited to contextualise selected outputs within their narrative accounts.	Narrative CV structure; qualitative evaluation criteria

<p>Core commitment 4: Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations</p>	<p>Evaluation is conducted in a context-sensitive manner at individual and team levels, without reference to institutional rankings or league tables.</p>	<p>Assessment framework; institutional evaluation guidelines</p>
<p>Supporting commitment: Commit resources to reforming research assessment</p>	<p>Dedicated governance structures, staff capacity, and technical resources were allocated to design, pilot, and refine new assessment tools and processes.</p>	<p>Steering and Executive Committees; pilot implementation</p>
<p>Supporting commitment: Review and develop assessment criteria, tools, and processes with researcher involvement</p>	<p>Researchers from all career stages were directly involved through surveys, focus groups, piloting phases, and iterative feedback cycles, ensuring contextual relevance and legitimacy.</p>	<p>Review of practices; survey report; focus groups; Narrative CV; rubric</p>
<p>Supporting commitment: Raise awareness and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training</p>	<p>Multiple meetings, training sessions, and training capsules were developed to support understanding, responsible use, and cultural change in assessment practices.</p>	<p>Training sessions; training capsules; internal presentations</p>
<p>Supporting commitment: Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning</p>	<p>The project actively participated in interinstitutional exchanges with other organisations committed to CoARA, fostering reflexivity and shared learning.</p>	<p>Interinstitutional workshops (e.g., IBEC session); shared materials</p>
<p>Supporting commitment: Communicate progress on adherence to the principles and implementation of the commitments</p>	<p>Progress, tools, and results were communicated through internal and external dissemination activities, supporting transparency and accountability.</p>	<p>Presentations; reports; openly shared materials</p>
<p>Supporting commitment: Evaluate practices, criteria, and tools based on solid evidence and research on research</p>	<p>Reform actions were grounded in longitudinal review, empirical survey data, qualitative focus groups, and iterative human–AI validation, aligned with state-of-the-art research on research assessment.</p>	<p>Review report; survey report; validation studies</p>

6. Outcomes and Preliminary Impact

The ReAss project has generated a set of concrete outcomes and has already produced early and observable impacts on research assessment practices, institutional reflection, and researcher engagement. While the project was conceived as a pilot, its scope and implementation have enabled changes that extend beyond experimentation and point towards longer-term institutional transformation.

The primary outcome of the project is the development of a coherent, CoARA-aligned research assessment model grounded in qualitative, contextualised, and peer-informed evaluation. This model is articulated through a set of interrelated outputs:

1. The Narrative CV Template – FPCEE Blanquerna, designed to recognise diverse research contributions, career trajectories, and collaborative practices, and to support reflective and meaningful assessment.
2. A shared qualitative assessment rubric, aligned with the European Framework for Research Careers (R1–R4), which promotes transparency, consistency, and responsible use of indicators while keeping peer judgement central.
3. A GenAI-supported decision-support model that provides structured qualitative feedback, visualisation, and aggregation of assessment data, explicitly conceived to complement—not replace—human evaluation.
4. A set of training and capacity-building actions, including multiple meetings, training sessions, and modular training capsules, aimed at supporting understanding, uptake, and responsible use of the new assessment tools.

Together, these outputs translate CoARA principles into operational practices that can be tested, refined, and scaled within the institutional context.

Early impact is already visible at multiple levels within the organisation. First, the Narrative CV and associated assessment model have been adopted as a regular reference for research assessment within three Research Institutes—Psychology, Education, and Sport Sciences—covering distinct disciplinary cultures. This adoption, supported by a structured capacity-building strategy, indicates that the reform has moved beyond an isolated pilot and has begun to shape routine assessment practices.

Second, the project has fostered a shift in researcher engagement and discourse around research assessment. Researchers involved in the pilot reported increased awareness of the diversity of research contributions, greater reflection on research trajectories and impact, and more explicit discussion of collaboration, mentoring, and societal engagement. Importantly, the project created legitimate spaces to articulate concerns, scepticism, and tensions, contributing to a more transparent and reflexive assessment culture.

Third, the project has initiated a reframing of assessment perspectives, particularly through the recognition of the tension between individual and group-based evaluation. The explicit incorporation of this dimension into the assessment framework represents an early conceptual impact with implications for how research environments, team science, and collective responsibility are valued institutionally.

Beyond immediate outcomes, the ReAss project has generated early signals of institutional anchoring. Strong commitment from research governance structures enabled the pilot to be integrated into

existing assessment cycles, and participation in the project was recognised as part of regular evaluation processes, facilitating engagement and legitimacy.

In addition, formal commitments from other faculties within the Universitat Ramon Llull to engage in similar reform processes indicate growing institutional interest and readiness for scaling. The public dissemination of tools, training materials, and presentations, alongside ongoing collaboration with national and international partners, further reinforces the project's visibility and potential influence.

While challenges remain—particularly regarding workload, evaluator capacity, and alignment with external accreditation systems—the outcomes achieved and the impacts observed suggest that ReAss has laid a robust foundation for sustained research assessment reform. The project demonstrates how evidence-based, participatory pilots can catalyse meaningful change while remaining attentive to institutional constraints and researcher concerns.

7. Conclusions

The ReAss project demonstrates that meaningful research assessment reform is both feasible and valuable when grounded in evidence, co-creation, and sustained institutional commitment. By translating the principles of CoARA into concrete tools, processes, and training actions, the project moved beyond a conceptual alignment with reform agendas and achieved tangible changes in assessment practices within its institutional context.

Rather than constituting an isolated pilot, ReAss functioned as a catalyst for broader reflection on the purpose, scope, and effects of research assessment. Its outcomes reveal both the potential of qualitative, narrative-based approaches to foster fairer and more inclusive evaluation, and the structural, cultural, and operational challenges that must be addressed to ensure sustainability and legitimacy over time.

7. 1. Lessons Learnt and Challenges

One of the main lessons learnt from the ReAss project is the critical role of institutional commitment. Strong and explicit support from research governance structures proved to be a decisive enabling factor, facilitating researcher engagement, legitimising experimentation, and allowing the pilot to be embedded within regular assessment processes rather than remaining peripheral. This commitment exceeded initial expectations and enabled the pilot to serve as a first step towards rethinking the institution's broader assessment framework.

A second key lesson concerns the value of co-creation and inclusive participation. The deliberate involvement of researchers from different career stages and disciplinary areas, as well as evaluators and technical staff, contributed to building trust, preventing resistance, and fostering a shared understanding of the reform's rationale. While scepticism and concerns persisted—particularly regarding feasibility and sustainability—the participatory design enabled these tensions to be surfaced and addressed constructively rather than undermining the process.

A third, and particularly significant, lesson was the need to explicitly align individual and group-based research assessment as a core dimension of reform. Assessment systems exclusively centred exclusively focused on individual outputs risk undermining collaboration, team development, and long-term research capacity. This insight led to the identification of a seventh dimension of change: aligning individual and group assessment to promote sustainable research ecosystems. Addressing this

dimension requires recognising collaborative roles, shared responsibility for research quality, and the contribution of research teams and environments alongside individual achievements.

At the same time, several challenges remain salient. Participants repeatedly expressed concerns about the sustainability of qualitative, narrative-based assessment, particularly in relation to workload, time investment, and evaluator capacity. The perceived objectivity and reliability of qualitative judgement, despite the use of shared rubrics and calibration efforts, also emerged as a persistent point of tension—summarised by some participants as “liking the music, but remaining sceptical about the lyrics”.

Another major challenge relates to alignment with external evaluation and accreditation systems. Although national and regional quality assurance agencies have begun to engage with CoARA principles, their assessment frameworks remain largely anchored in quantitative criteria. This misalignment continues to generate uncertainty among researchers and evaluators and underscores the need for institutions to navigate reform within a multi-level assessment ecosystem.

7.2. Transferability and Scalability

While the ReAss project is rooted in a specific institutional context, its design and outcomes offer transferable insights for other research-performing organisations engaged in assessment reform. The combination of evidence-based diagnosis, participatory co-creation, and iterative piloting provides a replicable methodological pathway rather than a fixed model.

Transferability lies less in the direct adoption of tools than in the principles underpinning their development: narrative and contextualised assessment, career-stage sensitivity, alignment between individual and team-based evaluation, and the centrality of peer-informed qualitative judgement. The successful implementation of the Narrative CV and associated assessment model across three research institutes representing distinct disciplinary cultures suggests that such approaches can be adapted to heterogeneous contexts.

Scalability, however, is contingent on sustained institutional investment in training, calibration, and governance. The ReAss experience highlights that scaling qualitative assessment requires not only technical tools, but also shared standards, evaluator confidence, and continuous dialogue. In this respect, the GenAI-supported decision-support model represents a promising mechanism to assist comparability and consistency during expansion, while remaining subordinate to human judgement.

7.3. Future Directions

Looking ahead, the immediate priority is to consolidate and stabilise the reformed assessment practices within the three research institutes involved in the pilot. Continued training, evaluator calibration, and reflective dialogue will be essential to reinforce confidence in qualitative judgement and to normalise narrative assessment as a legitimate and routine component of institutional evaluation.

In the medium term, the project outputs are expected to support the progressive extension of narrative-based assessment to additional faculties within the Universitat Ramon Llull. This expansion will require careful adaptation to disciplinary cultures where quantitative indicators have historically played a dominant role, as well as ongoing engagement with external accreditation requirements.

In the longer term, ReAss envisions research assessment reform not merely as a change in tools, but as a cultural transformation—one that values diversity of contributions, supports reflective career development, and aligns individual evaluation with sustainable research environments. Beyond institutional boundaries, the open dissemination of tools, training materials, and critical reflections positions the project as a reference case within the Catalan, Spanish, and European CoARA ecosystem.

Ultimately, the future impact of ReAss lies in its contribution to evidence-based, reflexive, and collective learning about how research assessment can be reimagined in practice, acknowledging both its transformative potential and its inherent tensions.